

FIGHT AGAINST OFFENSES. RESPONSIBILITY OF MILITARY SERVICES.

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Ubaydullayev Saidakbar Saydaliyevich

*Fergana State University
Faculty of Military Education
1st year student*

Sultonov Sardorbek

*Fergana State University
Faculty of Military Education
3st year student*

Annotation: *In this article, servicemen serving in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan deeply feel the responsibility of the people to reliably defend the Motherland. Soldiers are working diligently to improve their military skills, acquire equipment and weapons, and prepare for military service.*

Key words: *But in our military environment, there are some military personnel who violate military discipline.*

They are arbitrarily leaving the service, abandoning units on their own, evading military service, and falsifying documents.

Therefore, the fight against or prevention of these violations is an important condition for creating conditions for strengthening the rule of law in the military unit.

In our country, the fight against crimes committed in the military is carried out in strict accordance with applicable criminal law.

Criminal law consists of state law. These include the basics of criminal law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law on Criminal Liability for State Crimes and Laws on Liability for Other Types of Crimes (bribery, rape, hooliganism and petty theft, etc.).

The task of criminal law is to protect the social structure of Uzbekistan, the economic, property, personal, rights and freedoms of citizens from criminal aggression. In carrying out this task, the criminal law strictly defines what socially dangerous acts are considered a crime and the penalties to be imposed on the perpetrators.

The Criminal Code consists of general and separate parts. The General Part sets out the general statutes and grounds for criminal liability in accordance with

the principles of criminal law. The norms of a separate section specify the types of penalties to be imposed on offenders.

For crimes committed by citizens of Uzbekistan and stateless persons in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as abroad, according to the criminal legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, for crimes committed by foreign citizens in the Republic of Uzbekistan. will be prosecuted under the laws of Uzbekistan.

Military servicemen are criminally liable under the Law on Military Criminal Liability for war crimes committed on a common basis with other citizens of the state for the commission of state and general criminal offenses.

Criminal and punitive actions shall be determined by law in force at the time of committing these acts.

The law, which provides for penalties and mitigation of action, also applies to cases that took place before it was announced.

The law, which prescribes punitive action and increased penalties, does not have such force.

Criminal liability and punishment shall be imposed on persons accused of committing socially dangerous acts with intent or negligence specified in the criminal law.

Under the law, no one can be prosecuted without a court order. The only basis for social responsibility under the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the commission of socially dangerous acts, which have all the features of the crime, specified in the criminal law. The fact that a person's actions have all the features of a crime makes it possible to define this action under the relevant article of the criminal law. These are socially dangerous acts that violate the social structure, the economy, property, the individual, the rights and freedoms of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the rule of law, provided by criminal law.

Signs of crime include socially dangerous acts, wrongdoing, guilt, and criminal punishment for the act.

Social danger is an important material sign of a crime, which is the damage to the interests, social relations, protected by law.

These actions are illegal when we understand the danger of the act committed by the offender, who has a social risk in accordance with the norms of criminal law, and anticipate the dangerous consequences that may arise from it.

An important condition for a person to be found guilty is that he or she can be held accountable for his or her crimes before he or she reaches a certain age, and that guilty persons who have reached the age of 16 at the time of the crime can be

prosecuted. A person who is not accountable to the law for his or her crimes is a person who does not understand or control his or her actions due to his or her mental health at the time of committing the socially dangerous act. Such persons will be subject to medical treatment by the courts.

While committing a crime under the influence of alcohol does not exempt from criminal liability, as a general rule, intoxication is recognized as an aggravating circumstance.

General concept of war crime and its types. A war crime is an act for which a crime may be punishable by law.

Criminal punishment is a mandatory state measure applied by a court to a person convicted of a crime. Punishment is not only the punishment for a crime committed, but also the fairness of labor, strict observance of the law, correction and re-education in the spirit of respect for the rules of a democratic system, as well as new crimes committed by the perpetrators and others.

is also to prevent. It should be noted that punishment is not intended to inflict physical suffering or human dignity.

The following types of penalties may be imposed on offenders:

1. Imprisonment, transfer to a disciplinary battalion (for soldiers), transfer to a labor educational institution, correctional labor without deprivation of liberty, public prosecution, etc. may be applied.
2. Compensation for damage, deprivation of military rank (special rank).
3. Deprivation of the right to hold a certain position or the right to engage in certain activities, fines and dismissal.

Some of the punishments are complete abolition or life imprisonment. These punishments are very serious and dangerous crimes (treason, espionage, murder, large-scale theft, etc.).

Imprisonment is imposed for a period of 6 months to 20 years.

This punishment is served in correctional colonies (ICT-general, intensified, strict and special regime colonies and in some cases in prisons. . Is determined by the judgment of the colony.

All types of punishment are determined in accordance with the provisions of the Criminal Code. The court shall determine the penalty, taking into account the level of social danger of the crime committed, the person guilty, the circumstances that mitigate and aggravate the liability.

In practice, criminal law provides for the possibility of exemption from punishment in criminal liability, exemption from punishment, suspension of the exercise of the right, parole and employment.

The servicemen were prosecuted on a general basis together with other citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan for committing state and general criminal crimes. Liability for crimes committed by servicemen against the order of service is determined by the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The general provisions of criminal law are fully applicable to war crimes.

War crimes are crimes committed by military servicemen against the established procedures during the period of service, as well as crimes committed during the period of conscription.

A necessary condition for a war crime is the direction of action against the order of service established by the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Murder, crimes against state and legal property are not considered war crimes.

The perpetrators of war crimes may be conscripts, ie those who are serving in the military and those who are conscripted during military service.

War crimes provided for in the Criminal Code:

a) Crimes against the order of subordination and the observance of military honor. Disobedience to them, disobedience to orders, resistance to the boss, threats, insults to subordinates and violation of the rules of conduct. b) Crimes against the order of service, arbitrary unit, leaving the place of service, self-harm or refusal of military service by other means, violation of the rules of combat duty, internal duty Violation of the rules:

c) Violation of the rules of storage and use of military property, loss or destruction of military property, destruction or damage, violation of the rules of use of weapons, as well as dangerous substances and items, violation of the rules of registration and use of vehicles, flight preparation and flight violation of the rules, violation of the rules of ship management.

g) Crimes of military service Abuse of office, irresponsible attitude to service.

Failure to comply with the order of subordination is one of the gravest crimes, ie refusal to comply with the order of the chief, intentional disobedience to the order, according to Article 279 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, restriction of service for up to two years or up to one year shall be punished by imprisonment for a term of three to five years if the act was committed by a group of persons and caused grave consequences. The same act committed in a state of war is punishable by five to fifteen years in prison.

Failure to comply with the order (Article 280) shall be punishable by restriction of service for up to two years or transfer to a disciplinary unit for up to one year if negligent execution of the order causes extensive damage or serious consequences. The same act committed in a state of war is punishable by five to

ten years in prison. In mitigated cases, the provisions of the Disciplinary Code shall apply. Resistance to a commander (Article 281) is a war crime. is punishable by restriction or transfer to a disciplinary unit for up to 1 year or imprisonment for up to 5 years. Such acts are punishable by 5 to 15 years in prison if committed in a state of war. Intimidation of a commander Article 282. Intimidation of a commander with death or use of force in a state of war is punishable by imprisonment for a term of 3 to 5 years if there are sufficient grounds to commit such an act.

Injury to the skin.

A minor or moderate infliction of bodily harm to a officer is a restriction of service for up to 3 years or a transfer to a disciplinary unit for up to 1 year or up to 5 years if it is committed in the course of his military service or while performing it. is punishable by imprisonment. Severe bodily injury is punishable by 5 to 15 years in prison if committed by a group of individuals or with the use of a weapon. The above acts are punishable by 10 to 15 years in prison if committed in a state of war. Restriction of service for up to 3 years or imprisonment for up to 6 months or imprisonment for up to 5 years in case of abuse of office by a commander in the performance of his duties, or exceeding his authority, causing serious damage to the rights or interests of a serviceman or other citizen punished with. Those acts are punishable by 5 to 10 years in prison if they cause moderate to severe bodily injury.

Insult (Article 284) is an insult to the dignity of a person. Insulting a boss or subordinate is punishable by up to 2 years of restriction of service or up to 3 months of imprisonment or up to 3 years of imprisonment if committed after the imposition of a disciplinary sanction.

Violation of the rules of interaction between servicemen specified in the Statute (Article 285) consists of acts of violence committed by one serviceman against another (for example, the injury of one serviceman to another in order to make him perform his duties).) is punishable by up to 6 months in prison or up to 1 year in a disciplinary unit or up to 5 years in prison. If the crime is committed by a group of individuals or with the use of a weapon or with grave consequences, it is punishable by 5 to 10 years in prison.

Arbitrary abandonment of a place or part of service (Article 287) is punishable by disciplinary action for such acts of unexcused absence from work for more than one night and day, but not more than 10 days and nights. shall be punishable by imprisonment for a term of up to 6 months or up to 1 year of imprisonment in a disciplinary unit. is punished by deprivation.

Leaving the place of service, military unit for the purpose of refusing to serve in the military, transfer to another place, non-return to service from a service trip, vacation or medical institution is recognized as refugee.

Self-inflicted bodily harm, forgery of medical documents, or other frauds are criminal offenses, such as refusing to serve in the military. They are punishable by up to 6 months in prison or up to 1 year in a disciplinary unit with up to 5 years in prison.

Members of the military are criminally liable for selling personal items, military uniforms and equipment, mortgaging them, or giving them to other persons for use. These actions are punishable by up to 6 months in prison and up to 1 year in a disciplinary unit, and in mitigated cases, the provisions of the Disciplinary Code apply.

Loss or damage of weapons, ammunition and other military property provided for use in service is punishable by up to 2 years of restriction on service or up to 1 year of disciplinary correction or up to 3 years of imprisonment for violation of storage rules. The above acts are punishable by 3 to 5 years in prison if committed in a state of war. Violation of the rules of use of weapons (Article 297), as well as injuries in the use of weapons, explosives, radioactive or other dangerous substances, is punishable by up to 2 years of restriction of service or up to 5 years of imprisonment.

The death penalty is punishable by 10 to 15 years in prison. If the violation of the rules of driving and operation of military special or transport vehicles caused the accident, the perpetrators will be prosecuted and sentenced to up to 2 years of restriction of service or up to 5 years of imprisonment.

Violation of the rules of flight or preparation for them is punishable by imprisonment for a term of 5 to 10 years for violation of the rules of navigation of a ship, which caused the death of people.

Violation of the rules of military duty is one of the most dangerous crimes in the protection of territorial integrity, protection of water and air borders, prevention of emergency invasion of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

This crime consists of violation of military duty regulations, general requirements and is punishable by restriction of service for up to 2 years or imprisonment for up to 6 months or up to 1 year of disciplinary correction, or imprisonment for up to 5 years.

On September 22, 1994, the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the new Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which came into force on January 1, 1995.

The new Criminal Code is based on the rule of law, equality of citizens before the law, democracy, humanity, justice and is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development and goals of our young state.

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